

Efficacy of the ketogenic diet in overweight and obese patients

Eficacia de la dieta cetogénica en pacientes con sobrepeso y obesidad

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Abstract

Background: Obesity is the cause of multiple comorbidities responsible for severe cardiovascular events. The ketogenic diet is currently part of the treatment, by maintaining a balance of glucose metabolism. **General Objective:** To determine the efficacy of the ketogenic diet in overweight and obese patients. **Methodology:** Bibliographic review study, in the period October 5, 2021- November 10, 2022. **Database:** Science Direct, Cochrane, Pubmed, and Scopus, working with 83 scientific articles (55.42%: Q1, 16.6%: Q2, and 27.98%: Q3). **Results:** In a study with obese patients, polycystic ovary syndrome and liver disorders, the implementation of this diet obtained improvements in their symptoms. It should be noted that these studies were statistically significantly ($p=0.05$ relative to $p=0.003$). **Conclusions:** The ketogenic diet is an effective treatment in patients with obesity and overweight. Endorsed studies that demonstrate in depth the benefits of this diet are recommended.

Keywords: obesity, ketogenic, ketosis, carbohydrates, ketone bodies.

Resumen

Antecedentes: La obesidad es la causante de múltiples comorbilidades responsables de eventos cardiovasculares severos. La dieta cetogénica actualmente forma parte del tratamiento, al mantener un equilibrio del metabolismo de la glucosa. **Objetivo General:** Determinar la eficacia de la dieta cetogénica en pacientes con sobrepeso y obesidad. **Metodología:** Estudio de revisión tipo bibliográfica, en el periodo 05 de octubre del 2021- 10 de noviembre del 2022. **Base de datos:** Science Direct, Cochrane, Pubmed, y Scopus, trabajando con 83 artículos científicos (55,42%: Q1, 16,6%: Q2, y 27,98%: Q3). **Resultados:** En un estudio con pacientes obesos, síndrome de ovario poliquístico y alteraciones hepáticas, la implementación de esta dieta obtuvo mejoras en su sintomatología. Cabe recalcar que estos estudios fueron significativamente estadísticos ($p=0.05$ en relación a una $p=0.003$). **Conclusiones:** La dieta cetogénica constituye un tratamiento eficaz en pacientes con obesidad y sobrepeso. Se recomienda estudios avalados que evidencien a profundidad los beneficios que conlleva esta dieta.

Palabras clave; obesidad, cetogénica, cetosis, carbohidratos, cuerpos cetónicos,

Obesity, a pathology currently considered the pandemic of the XXI century. Its increase due to several factors and lifestyle changes, has become a public health problem, increasing the risk of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality and is considered the prelude of pathologies such as Diabetes Mellitus type 2, Arterial Hypertension¹.

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that approximately two billion of the adult population in the world is overweight, with 650 million obese². In Europe, the percentage of the overweight and obese population has increased by 50%³.

At least 2.8 million people die from being overweight, obesity and their co-morbidities regardless of social class⁴. In Latin America the percentages have been notably increasing, among the highest incidences we find: Mexico 32.4%, Spain 17%, Brazil, Argentina, Chile are in prevalences between 19.5 to 29.4%, Peru 19.7%^{5,6}.

According to the National Health and Nutrition Survey in Ecuador (ENSANUT 2016), the presence of overweight and obesity in adults was identified, with an increase in rural areas from 61.1% to 67.5% in 2016, while, in urban areas, a high level of 69.9% is maintained⁷.

This problem is multifactorial, such as socioeconomic and cultural stereotypes, which influence eating habits, considerably increasing sedentary lifestyles and reducing physical activity⁸. With the increase of obesity, while searching for a solution to this problem, an option to reduce weight and focus on a healthy lifestyle the application of the ketogenic diet has been studied. With the diet having the particularity of being high in fat, low in carbohydrates and low in protein⁹.

There are several schemes for the application of the ketogenic diet, depending on the goal that is sought in each person¹⁰. This diet is characterized by having a specific caloric intake according to the amount of macronutrients¹¹.

BACKGROUND ON THE KETOGENIC DIET

In 1921, Dr. Wilder prescribed the ketogenic diet (KD) in some patients with epilepsy, recommending its use for longer periods of time; observing that 52% of the treated patients were able to completely control their seizures and an additional 27% had improved their seizure control¹². In the 70's Dr. Atkins resumed the ketogenic diet again due to the cost of medicine, where he recommended the low-carbohydrate diet, with many more therapeutic objectives, applying it in patients with cardiovascular diseases¹³.

The ketogenic diet in 1990 demonstrated regulation of intestinal microbiota, inhibition of apoptotic factors; re-

sulting in upregulation of energy metabolism genes in the brain¹⁴. In 1997 "The story of Charlie" a two year old boy with intractable epilepsy was disclosed. This research allowed for great results such as the absence of seizures and considerable progress in normal child development"¹⁵.

DEFINITION OF THE KETOGENIC DIET;

It is considered as a diet that conforms high-fat and low-carbohydrate diets¹⁶, and belongs to the most effective class of diets to lose body weight quickly¹⁷. It is known for its capacity to elevate the circulating ketone bodies, producing what is called ketosis or also known as physiological or nutritional ketosis¹⁸. This ketosis is achieved by limiting carbohydrates in amounts lower than 50g or less than 10% of total consumption, while maintaining a protein concentration between 1.2-1.5 g/kg/d, with a predominance of fat consumption between 60-80%¹⁹. Ketosis is not always observed with this type of diet, being a consequence of the fact that up to 58% of the amino acids are glycolytic, therefore, the process of ketosis is avoided¹⁶.

KETOSIS

It is a metabolic change from the use of glucose derived from the liver to ketones containing adipose tissue to obtain caloric energy; where the absence of carbohydrates produces the separation of triglycerides, in fatty acids and glycerol. The liver converts the fatty acids into ketone bodies, which work as fuel for the tissues and especially for the central nervous system²⁰.

Ketosis is the process that accelerates the synthesis of ketone bodies. These circulate in the extra hepatic tissues where they are used as starting ATP precursors (adenosine triphosphate), reaching the brain, where it manages to cross the blood-brain barrier depending on the level of ketosis so that, as a result, ketones are transported through the plasma membranes²¹.

This condition of ketosis can be observed in prolonged fasting, type 1 diabetes, diets high in fat and low in carbohydrates; reaching the highest levels known to the so-called ketone bodies or ketogenesis, this occurs in the center of the mitochondria of the liver²². The overproduction of acetoacetic acid, generates ketonemia and ketonuria and results in the formation of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA from acetyl-CoA. It is emphasized that ketosis is a physiological mechanism, differentiating it from the pathological ketoacidosis observed in type 1 diabetes²³.

CLASSIFICATION OF THE KETOGENIC DIET;

The re-emergence of the Ketogenic Diet as one of the fast and effective ways to lose weight in the short term, gives as alternatives four main dietary therapies: Classic Ketogenic (CKD), Modified Atkins Diet (MAD): Effective for the treatment of severe obesity, Medium Chain Triglyceride Ketogenic Diet (MCTKD): Prevention of metabolic diseases and Low Glycemic Index Treatment (LGIT): Control of intractable epilepsy²⁴.

Classic ketogenic (CKD):

It was investigated by Wilder in 1921, this diet is rich in

fats and 90% of the energy consumed is used²⁵. It contains a very low amount of carbohydrates and an adequate amount of protein, considering that it should be adjusted according to the needs of each patient, for every 3 or 4 grams of fat adequately providing 1 gram of protein and carbohydrates²⁶.

The Adkins Diet (MAD)

Has demonstrated its advantages of a not so restrictive treatment, being this diet more accessible since its main advantage is that it allows more consumption of proteins and lipids; restricting the carbohydrates and its relation is 1-1 to 2-1, that is to say for each 1 or 2 g of fat there is 1g more of carbohydrates and proteins²⁷.

Medium Chain Triglyceride Diet

This diet is popular because it contains octanoic and decanoic fatty acids producing large amounts of ketones per kilocalorie of energy, leading to a decrease in total fat, it includes more carbohydrates and protein compared to the long chain triglyceride diet LCT²⁸; obtaining percentages of 19% CH (carbohydrates), 71% fat, 10% protein, which makes it a more pleasant diet, due to the higher intake of carbohydrates, but is accompanied by digestive effects that produce: cramping, vomiting, diarrhea, etc²⁹.

Low glycemic index treatment

This dietary treatment decreases the strict restriction of carbohydrates compared to the other KD. It is considered one of the most palatable and easy to implement. Foods with a low glycemic index that produce relatively small changes in blood glucose are limited³⁰.

MACRONUTRIENT COMPOSITION OF THE KETOGENIC DIET

For a diet to be considered as ketogenic, it is required to be represented by the restriction of carbohydrates, smaller amounts of between (30 - 50 g/day)³¹. The following classification exists according to the composition of the diet: the low calorie ketogenic diet (VLCKD), the isocaloric ketogenic diet (ICKD) and the low carbohydrate ketogenic diet (LCD)¹⁰.

Of the macronutrients, protein consumption preserves energy expenditure during the diet as it is considered to be the most satiating, followed by carbohydrates and finally fats³². The very low calorie ketogenic diets (VLCKD), are used for emergency treatment in cases of morbid or severe obesity, which provides a rapid weight loss and well tolerated by the patient³³.

The very low calorie ketogenic diet VLCKD, is characterized by formulations low in fat (10g/day of olive oil) and low in carbohydrates, these should be less than 30g/day and of vegetable origin, with protein content between 0.8 to 1.2 g/kg; which prevents the loss of total lean mass, as a result of the intake of 800kcal during 2 weeks of treatment application³⁴.

Alicia Albanesa demonstrated with evidence that patients used two different types of ketogenic diets in post-

operative bariatric surgery. The diets used were: the low calorie diet (VLCD) and the very low calorie ketogenic diet (VLCKD); obtaining favorable results in the latter, at the level of hemoglobin and surgical outcome, influencing the performance of drainage and hospital stay³⁵.

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE KETOGENIC DIET IN WEIGHT LOSS

The ketogenic diet is one of the excellent alternatives for overweight and obesity, due to the decrease of appetite that produces providing a feeling of satiety, due to the presence of ghrelin which stimulates appetite³⁶, as well as leptin, which is the hormone that inhibits the appetite and cholecystokinin; the latter is the one that suppresses appetite by interacting with proteins and lipids³⁷, by not consuming large amounts of protein, your weight loss is faster by losing fat, especially visceral fat, storing free fat³⁸, and having a low carbohydrate intake (< 50 g/day), 1 to 1.5 g of protein/ kg of ideal body weight, 15 to 30 g of fat per day, in total an intake of 500 to 800 calories³⁹. Since these values or parameters are easy to tolerate by most of the patients, it is estimated that 6 out of 10 patients remain with this treatment up to 2 years, however, it can present collateral effects⁴⁰.

The ketone bodies produced by the ketogenic diet are the result of the oxidation of fatty acids found in the liver and are taken to the extrahepatic tissues, where an energy producing glucose replacement is absorbed³⁴, resulting in physiological ketosis⁴¹.

Calorie decrease helps us in the reduction of visceral adipose tissue (VAT) in people with obesity⁴². A neuropeptide found in the lateral hypothalamus of the CNS is responsible for the process of regulating food intake, producing the storage or deposit of adipose tissue⁴³. A positive effect was observed with the low calorie ketogenic diet VLCKD, producing a decrease in visceral adipose tissue (VAT), adiposity and blood chemistry values. Short or long term dietary ketosis does not produce cytotoxic effect, nor increases oxidative stress; obtaining beneficial effects of the VLCKD in the orexigenic system, helping us to reduce obesity⁴⁴.

Cytokines are produced by cells that influence cellular interaction and communication. Therefore, cytokines have autocrine, paracrine and endocrine effects in different cell types⁴⁵. In contrast, adipocytes and leukocytes found in adipose tissue release pro-inflammatory cytokines and leptin, which act directly in a catabolic way on muscle cells and indirectly on insulin resistance, thus decreasing insulin absorption in muscle cells⁴⁶. The monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP-1) chemoattractant protein are found in higher levels in obese people, which explains the chronic inflammation produced by the increase of adipose tissue. It is observed that cytokines play an inflammatory role in the pathogenesis of obesity⁴⁷.

Roubenoff researched that aging is associated with the generation of catabolic cytokines, indicating that higher levels of the catabolic cytokines TNF-alpha and interleu-

kin-6 (IL-6) are associated with increased mortality in older adult patients⁴⁸. KD is shown to reduce fat mass in small deposits along with helping us in the reduction of visceral fat⁴⁹.

The presence of fibroblast growth factor 21 (FGF21), which act through the metabolic effects produced by KD, act directly on adipocytes; where FGF21 promote the elaboration and storage of adiponectin⁵⁰. Its effectiveness is materialized by reducing the consumption of carbohydrates below normal values, which leads to the synthesis of ketones. Subsequently, these ketone bodies are used as a means of fuel for the extrahepatic tissues, as well as for the central nervous system, skeletal muscle and heart^{20,51}.

One of the important effects of the ketogenic diet is that it produces a satiating effect, since fat and proteins are kept in the stomach for a longer time, thus lengthening the satiety process in the person; unlike carbohydrates that act in the appetite center, cholecystokinins and beta-hydroxybutyrate⁵², interacting as a sensitizer at the CNS level, decreasing the plasmatic concentrations of leptin and ghrelin. In conclusion, the ketogenic diet produces a decrease in the glycemic index by balancing plasma glucose concentrations⁵³.

Between the years 2016 to 2019 another study conducted on 73 patients with severe obesity, in which a nutritional treatment is performed for a period of 25 days with restriction of <800 kcal/day, obtaining notorious favorable results in the female group in relation to the male as follows: at the level of abdominal circumference (H 129 +20 M=140+- 13), body fat (H 44+-9 M 50 +-3) and fat free mass (H 80+-14) (M 59 +-8); which demonstrates the effectiveness of the ketogenic diet³³.

According to a study by Yeo Jin Choi, there is promising evidence of the ketogenic diet for short and medium term weight loss, demonstrating effectiveness in considerable weight loss in the first week, from the start of the diet, and then observing better results throughout its development⁵⁴.

In a 2013 meta-analysis, the very low-carbohydrate ketogenic diet was used, (less than 50 g of carbohydrate per day or < 10 % kcal of carbohydrate) and compared with low-fat diets < 30 % fat, for at least 1 year, obtained markedly greater weight loss than reduced-fat diets 0.01kg; 95% CI = 1.65 kg to =0.17kg p=0.02)⁵⁵. Rita Polito after using the very low calorie ketogenic diet observed a decrease in anthropometric values and BMI, in both lipid and hepatic profiles. Among these results, we can see: cholesterol T0 220.13+-50.77 t1 173.91+- 32.93 with p-value <0.05, triglycerides T0 126.54+-11 T1 90.25 +-14 p-value <0.05 AST-GOT u/l T0 22.17+- 5.98 T1 20.31+- 4.7⁵⁶.

Mariangela Rondanelli in 2021, conducted a study, using the VLCKD low-calorie ketogenic diet for a period of 3 months, observed a marked decrease in anthropometric parameters, body reduction by an average of 13.7 kg (from 98.9 to 85.2 kg), with an average BMI reduction of

33.7 kg/ m² to 29kg/m², and waist circumference with a decrease from 110.2 to 96.9 cm. No improvement in biochemical results was observed⁵⁷.

According to William S. Yancy jr., he obtained greater benefit in the low-carbohydrate diet groups, compared to those in the low-fat diet group of 12.9% versus 6.7%, with a p-value < 0.001. Decrease in fat mass by a total of 9.4 kg with the use of the low-carbohydrate diet, compared to the low-fat diet which only reduced by 4.8 kg. This was done in 120 overweight people, for a period of 24 weeks⁵⁸.

A study was done on patients with an average BMI of 43.5kg/weight who presented food addiction, assessed by three types of scales: binge eating scale, Yale food addiction scale and Yale-Brown obsessive-compulsive scale. Macronutrients were used, carbohydrates 10%, proteins 30% and fat 60%, giving a total of 5040 KJ per day in a period of 6 to 7 months. A good tolerance to the low carbohydrate ketogenic diet was obtained, with a reduction in addiction symptoms, anxiety, plus a 10 to 24% body weight loss, maintained at 9 to 17 months follow up⁵⁹.

A study by Juan Guo, Amber B. where certain patients had a low fat intake, using vegetables (10.3 % fat, 75.2% carbohydrates) versus a ketogenic diet of LC animal origin, with a decrease of carbohydrates (75.8 % fat, 10.00 carbohydrates). The participation of the study concentrated in 20 adults aged 29.9 with BMI 27.8+-1.3 kg-m, who were intervened for a period of 2 weeks; the result was the loss of LC weight. The loss was faster and more effective in the first week, reaching total values of 1.77+-0.32 kg (PAG< 0.0001) next week, in comparison with the LF diet that was slower; reaching, in the first and second week, a total reduction of 1.09+-0.32 kg (PAG=0.003). It is worth mentioning that the two results obtained were not so different in weight loss⁶⁰.

It can be evidenced that the ketogenic diet offers great benefits, with greater predominance at the level of weight as insulin resistance, but more studies are needed⁶¹.

Benefits of the ketogenic diet in other pathologies.

Worldwide more and more people suffer from obesity, metabolic syndromes and diabetes, which are increasing due to the presence of abdominal adiposity, leading to health problems such as insulin resistance, hypertriglyceridemia and hypertension; eventually leading to cardiovascular disease, diabetes, stroke and neurological diseases⁶². Factors such as age, genetics, gender, smoking, blood pressure, poor eating habits, T2DM, dyslipidemia, etc., increase the risk of cardiovascular damage. That is why it should be considered and kept in mind that the ketogenic diet has benefits (KD) at the cardiac metabolic level, acting as a cardioprotective antioxidant⁶³.

In a study conducted on the use of the KD ketogenic diet, in which 20 obese patients with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and hepatic alterations (p <0.05) were evaluated, the following results were obtained: improvement in

menstrual cycles, improvement in estradiol and progesterone levels, signs of fatty liver disappeared in six of seven study participants, the duration of the study was set at 12 weeks⁶⁴. Further studies are recommended to determine how it acts at the level of infertility, algomenorrhea and dermatologically in patients with polycystic ovary⁶⁵.

The very low calorie ketogenic diet in patients with moderate obesity, who present an alteration of the adventitial vasa vasorum (VV - is a thin layer fibroatheroma found in lipids), was applied to 20 participants with a very low calorie diet (VLCKD 600-800 Kcal/day) for 6 months, compared to 10 participants with Mediterranean diet of a reduction of up to (500kcal); obtaining as results in favor of the ketogenic diet an improvement in weight and total body fat, reducing endothelial dysfunction and improving the formation of atheromas compared to the Mediterranean diet that only acted on fat mass⁶⁶.

In addition to the above, the very low calorie diet (VLCKD), increases the benefits in epigenetic mechanisms (act against aging), involving methylene which is mediated by ketosis, helping in insulin resistance and avoiding cancer⁶⁷. However, we can observe that obesity and cancer are associated with each other by the presence of increased adipose tissue, forming between them the progression of tumors. Currently, alternatives are being sought to prevent the proliferation of cancer cells, such as weight loss by using the ketogenic diet⁶⁸.

The ketogenic diet also helps in neurological degenerative treatments, from a simple migraine to neurological tumors³⁹, being considered effective in substantially reducing the duration of migraine when using the ketogenic diet also known as "anti-headache" (AHD) It is considered effective in considerably reducing the duration of migraine when using the ketogenic diet, also known as "anti-headache diet" (AHD)⁶⁹.

In a trial conducted in 2020, where the ketogenic diet was used in obese patients with T2DM, it showed a greater decrease in glucose in patients who used the low calorie diet (VLCKD) with a value ($p < 0.0001$), improving the levels of HbA1c, triglycerides, total cholesterol and LDL, reducing the dose of insulin and oral drugs⁷⁰. This shows great metabolic benefits both at serum and lipid levels⁵⁴.

Physical endurance can be maintained despite discontinuation of carbohydrates in the daily diet, ketoadaptation takes time to maintain but adapts, compared to protein suppression, which has been shown to decrease performance in physical activity⁷¹. More research must be done to certify that the low-carbohydrate ketogenic diet does not produce a drop in the athlete's physical activity, both in strength and in endurance⁷². Obtaining with the ketogenic diet a loss of fat mass and visceral tissue in resistance training, maintaining lean body mass. Therefore, considering it not to be so efficient to increase muscle mass in men who have undergone 8 weeks of resistance training⁷³.

CONTRAINDICATIONS:

The ketogenic diet can present adverse effects when applied in short periods, such effects appear frequently in the first weeks of starting the ketogenic diet (KD), the most common are: nausea, hypoglycemia, diarrhea and dehydration⁷⁴; on the other hand, in extended periods, the adverse effects can be due to the metabolic effects of the diet such as: hypocitraturia, hypercalciuria, stunted growth, decreased bone density, anemia, and neuropathy⁷⁵. During the course and/or development of the diet there are adverse effects such as: gastrointestinal disorders, abdominal pain, emesis, constipation and gastroesophageal reflux⁷⁶.

In general, we find metabolic alterations such as pyruvate carboxylase alterations, which act as the main conductors of carnitine and porphyria, the latter two being responsible for conducting fats to the mitochondria and oxygen to the blood⁷⁷; considering that one of the important contraindications is the formation of kidney stones and the presence of dyslipidemia⁷⁸.

In the 1970s ketogenic diets produced fatal cardiac arrhythmias due to their misuse. One study showed that a low-carbohydrate, high-fat diet can lead to atrial fibrillation risk, but more research is needed to corroborate or verify this information⁷⁹, because in heart failure, the heart uses ketone bodies as a source of fuel, which are needed to produce cardiac output⁸⁰.

This diet is contraindicated in pregnant patients, since it can produce damages in the neural tube, producing a teratogenic effect. In the same way when lactating, this type of diet would not be advisable being a danger if it produces a ketoacidosis⁵⁵.

According to the guidelines of 2019, the European Association in charge of studying the liver, recommends an adequate consumption of proteins and calories to avoid hepatic encephalopathy and cirrhosis⁸¹, considering it of positive application in most studies, since it not only serves in weight loss but also works as a protector for the liver⁸². There is a desire to link the ketogenic diet with renal failure due to excessive protein intake, with a recommended consumption of 0.8kg to 1.4kg, remembering that red meat is the most harmful depending on the amount of consumption, but there is no evidence of damage in patients with chronic renal failure⁸³.

The ketogenic diet indicates us to be a treatment that can achieve great expectations in overweight and obesity, producing mild adverse health effects that can be treated with nutritional supplements in patients who use it.

At present there are different types of ketogenic diet, but the best known and used is the one that provides a reduced amount of carbohydrates and increased consumption of fats and proteins. Therefore, it is concluded that for its application it is necessary to have knowledge of the amount of carbohydrates to be used according to the type, such as, for example: protein, classic ketogenic, modified Atkins, etc.

The information was gathered from different articles, which indicate that the contraindications or adverse effects produced by the diet can be constipation and dyslipidemia, due to the high consumption of fats, which is easily treatable without any complications.

After this review, it is evident that the low-carbohydrate ketogenic diet has obtained more positive than negative results, since it produces the reduction of fat mass in patients with overweight and obesity, favoring the levels of triglycerides and cholesterol. It is for all these reasons that it is considered an ideal alternative for the treatment of these pathologies.

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